

Analytical modelling and design of linear controlled dynamic systems

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Abstract. A generalized canonical mathematical model of multidimensional controlled mining transportation complexes and other technical systems in form by A.M. Letov is considered. A principle of symmetry and an algebraic concept are in the basis of the developed analytical methods of design. A principle of symmetry is realized on a set of indexes of roots of a characteristic equation of the system and on a set of indexes of phase coordinates of the mathematical model. The problem of quality of dynamic processes in time is reduced to an algebraic problem of distribution of roots of a corresponding characteristic equation in a complex plane. An analogy in a procedure of transformation of a characteristic determinant into a polynomial and a structure of elementary symmetrical polynomials of roots is established. A new formulation of an analytical representation of change of phase coordinates in time in a form of ordered determinants with respect to indexes of roots and indexes of phase coordinates is obtained based on residue theorem. An illustration of the developed analytical method of design is performed on a special case of a well-known controlled technical system of the fourth order.

1. Introduction

Continuous improvements in the fields of mining technologies [1-4], transportation and hoisting [5-8], technological processes [9-12], and dynamics of technical systems [13-16] facilitate wider and more thorough development of analytical and computational simulation methods of processes and phenomena occurring within the systems.

Mathematical modelling as a tool for solving numerous problems of analysis and synthesis of complex systems, including technical, economic, biological, social, military and others, is being developed and improved along with computer technologies, mathematical apparatus, and is stimulated by the actuality of problems of the modern world. A correctly constructed mathematical model, which adequately describes the processes occurring in a studied system, is in the center of modelling. Mathematical models are constructed in a differential or algebraic form, based on fundamental laws and heuristic arguments. Multidimensionality, nonlinearity, stochasticity, and uncertainty are characteristic for models of complex systems.

Analytical solutions of multidimensional, linear dynamic systems in traditional notation have a massive form, where probability of making an error is high, and probability of detecting it is low. As the dimension increases, verification of results seems problematic. In particular, analytical solutions in

systems of linear differential equations are reduced to algebraic problems of finding the roots for corresponding characteristic equations. It is known that an analytical solution of complete algebraic equations above the fourth order is an open math problem to this day. A theory of modal control, a root hodograph method and other techniques are designed to get around this problem. The problem of verifying analytical solutions and mathematical models of dynamic systems is considered from a standpoint of general principles of symmetry, using symmetrization of mathematical description [17].

Models for problems of dynamics of mining transportation complexes and other technical systems are represented by systems of linear or nonlinear differential equations of finite order, obtained by heuristically constructed dynamic schemes, using the fundamental laws of Newton or classical results of analytical mechanics: Lagrange's equations, the Euler–Lagrange equation, Appell's equation of motion, and Hamiltonian mechanics [18-20]. In some special cases, differential equations allow analytical solutions and then modelling of the process is reduced to the analysis of this solution [21-24]. It is known that it has not been possible to establish regular, accurate analytical methods for solving systems of differential equations in a general form until the present day. Therefore, approximate, numerical methods for solving these problems are being developed, which are adapted to computer technology [25-27]. Thus, mathematical modelling is reduced to a computational experiment, performed according to a constructed mathematical model of the problem, while using the developed numerical methods. It is expedient to use matrix calculus as a mathematical apparatus here, which is convenient for compiling algorithms and their realization in a software. The development of a special calculus of monomial matrices for modelling the dynamics of mining transportation complexes and other technical systems is carried out in monographs [28-30].

The purpose of this paper is development of analytical methods of dynamic design of linear, multidimensional controlled mining transportation and other technical systems. The suggested analytical methods correspond to the theory of modal control, the root sensitivity, and the root locus. The problem of dynamics of multidimensional controlled technical system in time is reduced to an algebraic problem of distribution of roots of a corresponding characteristic equation in a complex plane.

2. Methods

A generalized canonical mathematical model of multidimensional controlled mining transportation complexes and other technical systems in form by A.M. Letov is considered. A principle of symmetry, symmetrical polynomials of roots, ordered determinants, constructed on sets of indexes of roots or indexes of phase coordinates are at the basis of the developed methods. Symmetrization ensures analytical solutions, which are mathematically elegant, reliable, and convenient for analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analytical modelling of multidimensional linear dynamic systems

Linear problems of dynamics of controlled mechanical systems are considered, a feature of which is a high dimension of systems of differential equations that describe dynamic processes. A generalized mathematical model of the dynamics of controlled mechanical systems is presented in a form of canonical matrix linear differential equations. The equations in special cases are reduced to well-known equations used in practice of dynamic design of mechanical systems. The problems of analysis and synthesis of multidimensional linear controlled systems are formulated based on algebraic representations. Methods of modal control are developed and analytical solutions of the formulated problems of analysis and synthesis are found on their basis. Focus is drawn to a necessity to find an expedient form of representation of the obtained analytical solutions in a form of ordered determinants. It is necessary in order to systematically describe extensive information about characteristics of a mechanical system, to eliminate possible errors and inaccuracies in a process of obtaining results in a systematized form for development of convenient computational algorithms.

Parametric synthesis and subsequent analysis of a dynamic quality are performed using recommendations of the method of distribution of roots, the root locus method, as well as the suggested description of dynamic processes in a form symmetrical with respect to root indexes and

phase coordinates. A unified approach to analytical determination of variable parameters by the required distribution of roots is developed on a basis of elementary symmetrical polynomials.

An algorithm for formation of coefficients of the characteristic equation through coefficients of the initial system of differential equations in a form of symmetrical determinants, structurally equivalent to symmetrical polynomials, is suggested.

A number of dynamic schemes of mechanical systems, which carry free and constrained moving masses under the action of a follower force or a force variable in direction, are considered. The Lagrange's and Euler–Lagrange equations of motion are compiled, dynamics and a possibility of stabilizing the motion by changing the centering or deviating the follower force and their combination are investigated. By applying the developed synthesis method for distribution of roots of the characteristic equation, the variable parameters of a mechanical system, which ensure the required dynamic quality, are determined analytically. Algorithms for combined control in one channel are constructed and investigated, and a possibility of ensuring dynamic stability based on incomplete information about a phase state of the system is shown.

A one-dimensional dynamic scheme of the simplest mechanical system is considered. It is an elementary dynamic element characterized by mass, elasticity and damping. Equations of free and constrained motion under kinematic and dynamic disturbances are constructed. A symmetrized analytical form of a dynamic process is indicated depending on roots of the characteristic equation, given initial conditions and external disturbances. The elasticity and damping coefficients, which ensure the required distribution of roots, are determined analytically.

3.2. Matrix model of linear dynamic systems and symmetrized form of analytical representation of free motion

A mathematical model of free motion of dynamic systems is reduced to a generalized matrix canonical form

$$\dot{X} = AX$$

as a system of n linear, homogeneous differential equations of the first order with constant coefficients under external disturbance given as a phase state of a system at the initial moment of time $X(0)$.

For $n = 1$ the mathematical model is reduced to its simplest form

$$\dot{x} = ax,$$

and analytical modelling is reduced to analyzing a trivial solution

$$x(t) = x_0 e^{at},$$

where x_0 is initial condition.

For $n = 2$ the mathematical model in expanded notation has a form

$$\dot{x}_1 = a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2,$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2,$$

and corresponds to a mathematical model of free motion for a simplest, one-dimensional dynamic element with $k = 1$, where k is degree of freedom of a system, meaning

$$n = 2k.$$

This mathematical model corresponds to the following expanded notation of an analytical solution for given initial conditions x_{10} , x_{20} and real, varied roots λ_1 , λ_2 of characteristic equation

$$x_1(t) = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} -x_{10} & a_{12} \\ -x_{20} & a_{22} - \lambda_1 \end{vmatrix}}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} e^{\lambda_1 t} + \frac{\begin{vmatrix} -x_{10} & a_{12} \\ -x_{20} & a_{22} - \lambda_2 \end{vmatrix}}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} e^{\lambda_2 t},$$

$$x_2(t) = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} - \lambda_1 & -x_{10} \\ a_{21} & -x_{20} \end{vmatrix}}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} e^{\lambda_1 t} + \frac{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} - \lambda_2 & -x_{10} \\ a_{21} & -x_{20} \end{vmatrix}}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} e^{\lambda_2 t}.$$

Characteristic equation of the considered system of differential equations

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} - \lambda & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0,$$

is reduced to an algebraic equation

$$a_2^{(2)} \lambda^2 + a_1^{(2)} \lambda + a_0^{(2)} = 0,$$

where coefficients of an algebraic equation are determined in a form

$$a_2^{(2)} = \begin{vmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix}; \quad a_1^{(2)} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & 0 \\ a_{21} & -1 \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} -1 & a_{12} \\ 0 & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}; \quad a_0^{(2)} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix},$$

or in an expanded notation

$$a_2^{(2)} = 1; \quad a_1^{(2)} = -a_{11} - a_{22}; \quad a_0^{(2)} = a_{11}a_{22} - a_{21}a_{12}.$$

According to Vieta's theorem the following is true

$$a_1^{(2)} = -(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2); \quad a_0^{(2)} = \lambda_1 \lambda_2,$$

from where determine the following

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11} + a_{22} &= \lambda_1 + \lambda_2, \\ a_{11}a_{22} - a_{21}a_{12} &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2. \end{aligned}$$

For an arbitrary n , an analytical solution of the original canonical model is represented in a symmetrical, ordered form with respect to indices of phase coordinates x_j and real, varied roots λ_k of a characteristic equation as follows

$$x_j = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\Delta_j(\lambda_k)}{\prod_{\substack{s=1 \\ (s \neq k)}}^n (\lambda_k - \lambda_s)} e^{\lambda_k t}; \quad (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n).$$

Here $\Delta_j(\lambda_k)$ is an ordered determinant formed from a phase coordinate index by replacing a column corresponding to number j in a characteristic determinant $\Delta_j(\lambda_k)$, by a state vector x_{i0} of a dynamic system at the initial time

$$\Delta_j(\lambda_k) = \sum_{i=1}^n (-x_{i0}) \Delta_{ij}(\lambda_k),$$

where $\Delta_{ij}(\lambda_k)$ is algebraic addition to a characteristic determinant $\Delta(\lambda_k)$ for a k^{th} root of the characteristic equation

$$\Delta(\lambda) = 0$$

of a matrix $A - \lambda E$.

The characteristic equation is reduced to an algebraic one

$$\sum_{i=0}^n a_{n-i}^{(n)} \lambda^{n-i} = 0,$$

where coefficients of an algebraic equation are in a form of symmetric determinants

$$i = 0: a_n^{(n)} = \det[-E];$$

$$i = 1: a_{n-1}^{(n)} = \sum_{j=1}^n \begin{vmatrix} -1 & 0 & \dots & a_{1j} & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & a_{2j} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & a_{jj} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & a_{nj} & \dots & -1 \end{vmatrix};$$

$$i = 2: a_{n-2}^{(n)} = \sum_{\substack{j,k=1 \\ (j < k)}}^n \begin{vmatrix} -1 & 0 & \dots & a_{1j} & \dots & a_{1k} & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & a_{2j} & \dots & a_{2k} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & a_{jj} & \dots & a_{jk} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & a_{kj} & \dots & a_{kk} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & a_{nj} & \dots & a_{nk} & \dots & -1 \end{vmatrix};$$

.....
 $i = n: a_0^{(n)} = \det[A].$

According to Vieta's theorem, coefficients of an algebraic equation are also determined by the symmetrical polynomials of roots

$$i = 1: a_{n-1}^{(n)} = (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j;$$

$$i = 2: a_{n-2}^{(n)} = (-1)^{n-2} \sum_{\substack{j,k=1 \\ (j < k)}}^n \lambda_j \lambda_k;$$

.....
 $i = n: a_0^{(n)} = (-1)^0 \prod_{j=1}^n \lambda_j.$

From where n algebraic functional dependencies of roots of a characteristic equation and coefficients of the canonical model of a dynamic system are determined.

3.2.1. Analytical modelling of free motion of a one-dimensional dynamic element

A calculation scheme of a one-dimensional dynamic element is shown in the following figure 1.

A dynamic element during one-dimensional motion $x(t)$ of a point mass is characterized by kinetic energy of translational motion T , by potential energy of elastic forces E_e , and by dissipative function of damping forces Φ , which in this case are determined by trivial formulas

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m \dot{x}^2, \quad E_e = \frac{1}{2} c x^2, \quad \Phi = \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{x}^2,$$